

Preparation and Characterization of Solid-State Electrochemical Sensor for the Determination of Ni(II)

*Rajendra Maharjan, Krishna Badan Nakarmi and Amar Prasad Yadav**

Central Department of Chemistry, Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

**Email: amar2y@yahoo.com*

Abstract

A simple method was used for the preparation and characterization of solid-state electrochemical sensor based nickel sulfide and silver sulfide co-precipitate for the determination of Ni(II) ions in aqueous solutions. This solid-state electrochemical sensor has been characterized in terms of direct potentiometry, potentiometric titration, selectivity coefficient, dynamic time response and pH range. Characterization of prepared precipitates by X-ray diffractometry (XRD) depicted the presence of binary phase of NiS and Ag₂S existing as separate phase. The sensor exhibited a good Nernstian response of 28.75mV per decade for Ni(II) ions over a wide concentration range of $1.0 \times 10^{-1}M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-6}M$ by using ascorbic acid, methanol and NaNO₃ (a buffer solution) to the Ni(NO₃)₂ test solution. The dynamic time response of the solution was found to be in <2 minutes for the stability of potential within $\pm 1mV$. The sensor is suitable for use in aqueous solutions in a wide pH range of 2.0–7.0. The electrode has shown a high selectivity for the Ni(II) ions over a wide variety of other cations. The electrode was successfully applied as an indicator electrode in potentiometric titration of Ni(II) ions against EDTA. These data show that the sensor can be used as an effective tool for determining the Ni(II) content of water samples.

Keywords: *Ion-Selective Electrode, Selectivity, Potentiometry, Electrochemical Sensor, Solid-State*

Introduction

The increasing number of potentially harmful pollutants in the environment calls for fast and cost-effective analytical techniques to be used in extensive monitoring programs. Heavy metals are currently the cause of some of the most serious pollution problems. Even in small concentrations, they are a threat to the environment and human health because they are non-biodegradable. People are constantly been exposed to heavy metals in the environment. The dangers associated with heavy metals are due to the ubiquitous presence of these elements in the biosphere, their bioavailability from both natural and anthropogenic sources, and their high toxicity [1]. The maximum recommended concentration of Ni(II) ions in drinking water for livestock is 2.5 mg/ml [2]. Nickel is well known as a toxic metal that can cause cancer of nasal lungs, dermatitis, asthma, and disorders of central nervous system [2]. US EPA has classified nickel as one of 13 priority metal pollutants for its widespread use [3]. The metal contaminants most commonly observed in the environment are: nickel, lead, chromium, zinc, mercury, cadmium and copper.

The detection and quantification of heavy metal ions are important in many applications, including environmental monitoring, waste management, developmental biology and clinical toxicology [4]. This technology has received a lot of attention in the last decade for the fabrication of electrochemical sensors for various applications. The need for developing a sensor that is fast,

* **Corresponding author**

accurate, reproducible and above all, selective to the ion of interest is the main reason for the quantum leap [5]. Potentiometric detection based on ion selective electrodes (ISE's), are a simple method, offers several advantages, such as ease of preparation and procedures, simple instrumentation, relatively fast response, wide dynamic range, reasonable selectivity and low cost. In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the field of ISE's based on all solid-state contact free of inner reference solution [6].

An Ion-Selective Electrode (ISE) produces a potential that is related to the concentration of an analyte due to the charge separation through the chemisorption of primary ion from the solution phase onto the surface of the electrode while the counter ions accumulate in the solution phase [7]. According to the Nernst equation:

$$E_{\text{cell}} = E^0 \pm (RT/nF) \ln[a_x]$$

When measuring nickel ions, (i.e. $n = +2$), the ideal slope factor at 298 K (25°C) has a value of 29.58 mV.

Experimental

Reagents

All the reagents used were of analytical reagent grade.

Apparatus

The Ni(II) ion selective electrode as working electrode and calomel electrode (Hg/Hg₂Cl₂) as reference electrode were used and in between the circuit connecting these electrodes, a high impedance multimeter (BK Precision model-389, Taiwan) was connected in order to measure the potential given by the Ni(II) ISE.

The hot air oven (Narang Scientific Works Pvt. Ltd.), pH meter (model-276), magnetic stirrer (Stuart Scientific from UK) ultra-sonicator (Baanson-2510) and IR-based machine (manufactured in UK) were also used for this purpose.

Electrode preparation

In this work, the nickel ion selective electrode based on NiS/Ag₂S at 2:1 mole ratio in the form of pellet was prepared by co-precipitation method as;

A thin silver disc was made as per the size of the pellet and then inserted inside the polyethylene rod for silver back-contact with the help of silver paste. The membrane side of the electrode was then polished in #2000 grit sized SiC abrasive paper for smooth and well-polished nickel ion selective electrode. The sensor was finally conditioned for 24hrs by soaking into 1.0 × 10⁻³M Ni(NO₃)₂ solution.

Potential measurements and calibration

Potentials were measured at room temperature (25±5°C) on a multi-meter. A standard saturated calomel reference electrode was used in conjunction with the fabricated Ni(II) sensor as working electrode. A salt bridge (KNO₃ in agar-agar) was used to connect the two electrodes. The electrochemical cell assembly for potential measurements can be represented as:

Results and Discussions

Characterization of co-precipitate

X-ray diffraction pattern of NiS-Ag₂S co-precipitate was taken in the diffraction angle of 20 to 50 degrees as shown in Fig.1. All the peaks were assigned based on the JCPDS database and showed the presence of binary phase of NiS and Ag₂S existing as separate phase.

There were some peaks for the Ni-metal on the extreme left side of the XRD pattern. The presence of small amount of metal in the co-precipitate is assumed to be beneficial for enhancing the electrical conductance.

Figure 1: XRD pattern of Ag₂S-NiS co-precipitate

Working pH of the electrode

The working pH of the test solution having concentration of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ was successfully determined at room temperature. Figure 3.2 showed the potential response of the sensor on the pH of the test solution of a fixed concentration. The pH range of 2.0 to 7.0 was taken as the working pH range of the Ni(II) sensor as no interference from H⁺ ions or OH⁻ ions was observed. The cause of considerable potential drift at the acidic solution i.e. at lower pH may be due to the protonation of the membrane of the electrode to some extent causing strong response to the H₃O⁺ ions concentration i.e. competition of H⁺ ions against Ni(II) ions. It is noteworthy that in alkaline solution, the observed drift at higher pH values could be due to the hydrolysis of nickel in the test solution.

Figure 2: Effect of the pH of on the potential response of the Ni(II) ion-selective electrode

Direct potentiometry study

Response of NiS/Ag₂S ISE to Ni²⁺ ions

The plots of the potential response of the electrochemical cell against the concentration of the test solution were shown in Figs. 3-6. The outcome of the direct potentiometry of Ni(II) ion selective electrode for Ni(II) ions revealed the Nernstian slope of 15.59mV/decade as shown in Fig. 3. The electrode exhibited the potential response in the linear range of $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{M}$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$ concentration. It seemed that without the presence of any anti-oxidants or other non-aqueous solvents, the value of Nernstian slope of the electrode was greatly affected and resulted in less than the predicted theoretical Nernstian slope.

Figure 3: Plot of potential vs. concentration in a mixture of Ni(NO₃)₂ and NaNO₃

Figure 4 depicted the experimental work based on standard addition method with the test solution composed of a mixture of Ni(NO₃)₂, NaNO₃ (ISAB) and methanol. The Nernstian slope was not improved with only 12.95mV/decade and may be due to the low conductance and low Ni²⁺ ions transport through the sensor membrane. But it can be concluded that at lower concentration there was sharp change in potential response which may be due to the presence of methanol that help in the improvement of the detection limit with even lower concentration beyond $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$ solution.

Figure 4: Plot of potential vs. concentration in a mixture of Ni(NO₃)₂, methanol and NaNO₃

In this regard to find the optimum Nernstian response, methanol was replaced by ascorbic acid (an anti-oxidant) to the test solution. Fig. 5 shows a very good Nernstian slope of 28.38mV/decade with respect to the theoretical Nernstian slope of 29.58mV/decade. But, in this case, the experimental data were slightly scattered and dispersed.

Figure 5: Plot of potential vs. concentration in a mixture of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, ascorbic acid and NaNO_3

By using both the methanol and ascorbic acid to the test solution, a uniform slope with good Nernstian response of 28.75mV/decade and lower detection limit of $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$ $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ ion concentration as shown in Fig.6 was obtained.

Hence, the potential response of the $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ ion selective electrode was greatly dependent upon the composition of the test solution and the best result was obtained with the mixture of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, NaNO_3 , ascorbic acid and methanol.

Figure 6: Plot of potential vs. concentration in a mixture of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, ascorbic acid, methanol and NaNO_3

Potentiometric titration

Potentiometric titration of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution against EDTA solution

The applicability of the $\text{NiS}/\text{Ag}_2\text{S}$ ion selective electrode, as an indicator electrode for the potentiometric titration, was examined by the titration of 10ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ concentration of

$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution against $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ concentration of EDTA and the end-point was found to be at 10ml, Fig. 7.

The emf of the cell with respect to the concentration of Ni^{2+} and S^{2-} during potentiometric titration was shown by the equation below;

$$E_{\text{cell}} = E_{\text{aggreg}} + 0.0295 \log [\text{Ni}^{2+}]/[\text{S}^{2-}] \quad \rightarrow \quad (3)$$

The emf of the cell depends on the concentration ratio of $[\text{Ni}^{2+}]/[\text{S}^{2-}]$. When Ni^{2+} ion solution was titrated against EDTA solution, observed emf of the cell was decreased due to the formation of Ni-EDTA complex from free Ni^{2+} ions of the solution. The differential curve of that titration was also drawn to locate the end-point precisely.

Figure7: A Potentiometric titration curve of $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ ion solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{molL}^{-1}$) with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{molL}^{-1}$ EDTA using the proposed membrane sensor as an indicator electrode

Leaching behavior of the sensor membrane

For the determination of the amount of the $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ ions leached into the aqueous solution from the sensor membrane, the electrode was dipped in diluted solution of 5ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution for 3hrs. The test solution was titrated against $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ EDTA solution. The typical titration curve obtained was shown in the Fig. 3.8.

Figure 8: A Potentiometric titration curve of Ni^{2+} ion solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{molL}^{-1}$) with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{molL}^{-1}$ EDTA

From Fig. 8, it can be estimated that for the consumption of 5ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ molL}^{-1} \text{ Ni(NO}_3)_2$ solution, exactly 6ml solution of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ molL}^{-1} \text{ EDTA}$ solution was required. But here, 1ml of excess volume of EDTA was consumed by dissolved $\text{Ni(NO}_3)_2$ solution from sensor membrane. Hence by calculation, $5.869 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g}$ or ($4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) of Ni^{2+} ions of the Ni(II) sensor membrane has been leached into the diluted aqueous solution of $\text{Ni(NO}_3)_2$ after dipping the electrode for 3hrs. The leaching of sensor membrane may be due to the setup of the concentration gradient between sensor membrane and test solution as well as the ion exchange phenomenon.

Leaching behavior of the sensor membrane in $0.1 \text{ molL}^{-1} \text{ NaNO}_3$

The leaching of the membrane of the electrode was also examined into NaNO_3 solution in order to understand its stability in corroding medium. The electrode was dipped into diluted solution of 5ml of 0.1M NaNO_3 solution for 3hrs. The test solution was titrated against $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M EDTA}$ solution as in previous experiment. The titration curve obtained was not standard sigmoid, but an 'L' shaped curve as depicted in Fig. 3.9. It may be because of the high sodium concentration and its interference as disodium salt of EDTA is used for potentiometric titration [8]. The typical titration curve obtained by this phenomenon was shown in the Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Potentiometric titration curve of NaNO_3 ($1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ molL}^{-1}$) with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ molL}^{-1} \text{ EDTA}$

Here, 8ml of EDTA solution has been consumed by the $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ molL}^{-1} \text{ NaNO}_3$ solution. As the solution did not contain the Ni^{2+} ions, the consumption of EDTA solution was due to Ni^{2+} ions dissolved from the NiS/Ag₂S sensor membrane after dipping it for 3hrs in NaNO_3 solution. So, $4.695 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g}$ ($3.199 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) of Ni^{++} ions of the membrane has been leached into the diluted NaNO_3 solution after dipping the electrode for 3hrs. Almost the leaching of the sensor membrane in 0.1M NaNO_3 was eight times in comparison to the leaching phenomenon in $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M Ni(NO}_3)_2$ solution. This was due the absence Ni^{2+} ions in the NaNO_3 solution causing high concentration gradient between the membrane sensor and the test solution of NaNO_3 .

Fig. 10 depicted the sensor membrane of the electrode at which the nickel ion was gradually leaching out of the pellet of the Ag₂S/NiS sensor when kept in the moist environment for about 6-7 months without any use. This happened due to the aerial oxidative leaching of the nickel present in the crystal lattice of the pellet as well as the hydration of the sensor membrane to give the greenish crystal of the nickel.

Figure 10: Spontaneous leaching of the membrane sensor after long storage in the moist environment

Dynamic Response Characteristics

During characterizing the dynamic response time of a Ni(II) sensor, the potential was measured in every 10-fold difference in concentration from $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{M}$ of the Ni(II) salt solution.

From the Fig. 11, it was observed that the equilibrium potential has been set up within 2 minutes after the electrode was dipped into the test solution. The average time required for the electrode to reach within $\pm 2 \text{mV}$ potential of the final equilibrium value after successive immersion in a series of Ni^{2+} ion solutions.

This may be probably due to the fast interaction kinetics of Ni^{++} ions of the test solution with the membrane sensor at the test solution/membrane interface, solubility product of the solid-state electrode with lower resistance of the sensor as well as good polishing and optimum preconditioning of the membrane electrode.

Figure 11: Dynamic response time of the Ni(II) sensor for step changes from low to high concentration of Ni^{2+} ions.

Selectivity coefficient determination

In this experiment, the potentiometric selectivity coefficients, describing the preference of the membrane for Ni(II) ions relative to an interfering ion, were determined by the matched potential method (MPM) [9, 10].

As can be seen from the data given in Table-1, it was obvious that the proposed Ni(II) solid-state sensor was highly selective to Ni^{2+} ion unlike other common cations such as NH_4^+ , Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . The selectivity coefficients were on the order of 1.0×10^{-2} or smaller, indicating that

the presence of interfering ions did not significantly disturb the functioning of the Ni(II)selective electrode.

Table 1: The selectivity coefficients of various interfering cations for Ni⁺⁺ membrane sensor

Interfering ions	$K_{Pot,MPM}$	$\log K_{Pot,MPM}$
NH ₄ ⁺	4.922×10^{-3}	-2.307
Ag ⁺	2.892×10^{-2}	-1.538
Cu ²⁺	1.210×10^{-2}	-1.917
Pb ²⁺	5.708×10^{-3}	-2.243
Zn ⁺⁺	3.703×10^{-3}	-2.431
Cd ⁺⁺	5.480×10^{-3}	-2.261

Practical applications of laboratory fabricated sensor

The fabricated NiS/Ag₂S solid-state sensor described in this work offered stable, reliable, sensitive and selective tool for the quantitative determination of Ni(II) ions in some important matrices like electronic industrial waste solution.

Conclusion

The solid-state electrochemical sensor has been prepared based on nickel sulfide and silver sulfide co-precipitate for the determination of Ni(II) and then characterized. The Ni(II) sensor exhibited linearity over a wide concentration range ($1.0 \times 10^{-1}M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-6}M$) with Nernstian slope (28.75 mV/ decade of activity) by using ascorbic acid, methanol and NaNO₃(a buffer solution) to the Ni(NO₃)₂ test solution, fast response time (<2min.), wide pH range (2–7) long lifetime (6–7 months) and selectivity (of the order of 10^{-2}) over a number of cations. Hence, the characteristics of the presently developed sensor are comparable with commercially available sensors. The electrode was successfully applied as an indicator electrode in potentiometric titration of Ni(II) ions against EDTA. These data showed that the sensor could be used as an effective tool for determining the Ni(II) content of water samples.

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